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EAJADE

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DELIVERABLE REPORT

DATA MANAGEMENT PLAN

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Data Management Plan

Executive summary:

This report describes the data management prospects for the data generated, collected and processed by the EAJADE project. Like for all Horizon-Europe projects, the first version of this DMP was submitted by month 6 of the project. Updated versions will later deliver snapshots of the project's data management implementation.

1. INTRODUCTION

EAJADE is a training and staff exchange network for accelerator R&D within elementary particle physics, with a focus on future Higgs factories (as prioritized by the latest update of the European strategy for particle physics) and related technologies. EAJADE addresses the need of exchange of ideas on R&D and implementation of such a future accelerator, on generic technical developments, and on investigations into new and sustainable technologies. EAJADE does so by exchanging accelerator scientists and experts between Europe, America (Canada and USA), and Japan.

As emphasized also in the project proposal, FAIRness and openness of science and its tools and results are of high value for EAJADE.

However, as was indicated in the EAJADE proposal, for small and medium scale accelerators, which are the main facilities where we will conduct our research, FAIRness and openness of data are generally difficult topics (unlike in many other scientific fields, e.g. astrophysics, and now also to some extent HEP experiments, where some levels of data are nowadays used even by theorists...). To a large extent, this is because the work on accelerators is a mix of scientific research and engineering development, with many unique one-of-the-kind objects, even prototypes, for which measurement data will only be interesting to the few people working on them, with little generality or usefulness to other scientists, even to other accelerator scientists. The same is true for most simulation data, as they will in general be specific to one of the given facilities.

This is not to say that absolutely no data from accelerator operation and R&D can be of general interest, but one exercise of EAJADE certainly needs to be to define exactly what kind of data may or may not be suitable for sustainable data storage, interoperability, etc. Updates to the present data management plan will be used to document our progress in this respect.

So while we certainly acknowledge the overall goal of making also our data findable, accessible, interoperable, and reusable, a practice on this has still to be defined and established, also in discussions with the international partners that have very different approaches to FAIRness and openness. We hope that EAJADE can contribute to this endeavour.

There is, moreover, another point to be considered: EAJADE does never constitute the main funding source for any given accelerator R&D project – it merely adds to the project by allowing for researcher mobility. EAJADE can, therefore, not claim any ownership of the experimental or theoretical data generated during EAJADE secondments.

A great deal of available data can nonetheless already now serve as an example of FAIRness and openness. That is why we plan to publish all our deliverables and results

in the EAJADE community created on Zenodo¹ and to publish our code in GitHub. Survey and personal data, which are the only sensitive data in EAJADE, are recorded in a private SharePoint environment – the DESY Sync&Share cloud environment – only accessible to project members.

A Data Management Plan (DMP) is a key element of good data management as it is the initial tool to implement our FAIR data policy. This document is the first outline of our idea on data management for the EAJADE consortium, and later versions will give snapshots of the data management implementation progress in the programme.

This document is organized as follows: After a summary of the data collected and generated in the project in chapter 2, we describe in chapter 3 how the FAIR principles might in the future be applied to EAJADE data. Finally, the DMP addresses resources, security and ethics.

This document follows the EC – H2020 FAIR DMP template provided in the EC portal².

2. DATA SUMMARY

EAJADE mainly performs R&D and implementation studies for technologies and methods for future colliders. Consequently, data are generated in a variety of different ways, by different people and at different accelerator facilities throughout the world, with typical storage locations at these facilities – that follow different data management policies (USA, Japan, Canada). The latter point is of particular interest concerning the FAIR principles since typically the data management regulations of the facilities apply – and do not always easily comply with our and the EU’s thinking about FAIRness and openness. Furthermore, as written above, EAJADE cannot claim data ownership in most cases.

EAJADE will nevertheless strive to implement – and be it only for testing and prototyping purposes – a FAIR data repository for (some of) its instrument and simulation data, linking to a metadata catalogue comprising all data of the project. This infrastructure is currently under development at DESY. In the case of existing data sets being re-used, the data policy and the infrastructure of the hosting partner facility are complied with.

The documents, metadata schemas and source code produced by EAJADE are mostly useful to accelerator scientists.

¹ <https://zenodo.org/communities/eajade/>

² https://ec.europa.eu/research/participants/docs/h2020-funding-guide/cross-cutting-issues/open-access-data-management/data-management_en.htm

Two areas come to mind, when thinking of the EAJADE research topics, that might prove particularly well suited for a first application in the accelerator R&D world:

- One area of development with potential for making data publicly available is in the context of artificial intelligence (AI) applied to accelerator operation and optimisation. A huge number of accelerator parameters, both from continuous measurement by beam instrumentation as well as associated environmental data, are normally made available widely within the community working on a given accelerator. Large parts of such data are also archived for later analysis by the experts working on the commissioning and optimisation of the facility. Nowadays, AI methods based on neural networks and other schemes are used to find trends and enable predictions of various "events" affecting the accelerator operation, or to optimise parameters without necessarily having a full model available as guide, even to help ensure safety and security of the devices. Defining relevant "paradigmatic" datasets for later use by AI experts could be a concrete and highly appreciated aim.
- Another area where data sharing could be of interest is the laser-plasma acceleration field, in particular simulation data sets.

Table 1 gives an overview of the various data types planned or considered by EAJADE.

Table 1: Data generated, processed and collected by EAJADE

Data type	Origin	Expected size	Contents
Text documents	PCs, consortium cloud spaces, online document editors like Overleaf	100s of Megabytes	Deliverable reports, meeting minutes, documentation
Presentations	PCs, consortium cloud spaces, online document editors like Overleaf	100s of Megabytes	Training material, dissemination and communication material, presentations at conferences
Videos	PCs	Few Gigabytes	Training material, dissemination material
Metadata schemas and example files	GitHub, Nexus / HDF5 format, etc.	10s of Megabytes	Adopted ontologies for metadata catalogues
Source code	GitHub, several EAJADE facilities	10s of Megabytes	Extension and integration of existing catalogues and services

Data sets	All EAJADE facilities	Terabytes	Experimental measurement results and computer simulation input and output data
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3. FAIR DATA

The FAIR principles³ and the demand for open science practices will have their impact on the EAJADE project and its data management. In the following, we sketch our ideas and plans for each of the four FAIR dimensions.

As described, this approach and project goal is a challenge for the EAJADE project since there is no deeply rooted tradition of implementing FAIR principles for this kind of often small-scale research data in this field of science. Also, the question of which data set to keep for what time and which (potential) user community needs to be addressed by the project.

3.1. MAKING DATA FINDABLE, INCLUDING PROVISIONS FOR METADATA

All public deliverables of the project are uploaded to Zenodo and thus assigned a doi and automatically harvested by the EOSC search portal⁴. Once approved by the European Commission, all EAJADE results are also findable in CORDIS.

Also relevant talks, presentations, and training materials will be published via Zenodo.

In order to allow tracking of instrument and simulation data and software produced in EAJADE, – given consent of data owners – they will receive entries in the metadata catalogue at DESY, where possible with links to the relevant data or software repositories and storage locations⁵. As far as reasonable and useful, data sets without another “home” will be stored in a dCache-based EAJADE data repository with metadata catalogue backend to be made operational at DESY.

3.2. MAKING DATA OPENLY AVAILABLE

As discussed above, all public EAJADE deliverables, reports, talks, presentations, and training materials are openly accessible in Zenodo.

³ M. Wilkinson et al., The FAIR Guiding Principles for Scientific Data Management and Stewardship, *Scientific Data* 3 (2016) 160018.

⁴ <https://search.marketplace.eosc-portal.eu/search/all?q=eajade>

⁵ The data hosts will apply their own authentication and authorization measures, steering access to the data.

The access to confidential deliverables is provided by the SharePoint collaboration space through nominative accounts for project participants. Only a few deliverables are not public because they contain sensitive data (Collaboration Agreement, ethics, human resources allocation, industrial knowhow, and trade secret). Anonymous access to public deliverables is guaranteed. For confidential deliverables, the identity is ascertained using SharePoint's credentials.

As far as made possible by their owners, data sets and software will be made available – potentially after embargo periods – if they are of sufficient scientific interest. This will be facilitated using the mentioned metadata catalogue linking either to the data management systems of the individual research facilities at which EAJADE work takes place or to the DESY-based data repository.

3.3. MAKING DATA INTEROPERABLE

Only widely used or open-source software is needed to read and modify the project documents (e.g. PDF, MS suite, LibreOffice suite). The code source, Git tool set and software catalogue are written in standard and widespread languages.

Most data used in accelerator R&D are based on the HDF5, Nexus and OpenPMD formats, all of which are open and well-documented community standards.

4. ALLOCATION OF RESOURCES

Zenodo is hosted by CERN and receives long-term funding from CERN, the European Commission and other foundations. GitHub is financed through sponsorship and with premium subscription plans for private companies. It is free to use for individuals and academia. Human resources dedicated to FAIR in ExPaNDS were included in its Grant.

WP leaders are responsible for the data management of their own products, with WP6 ensuring the overall compliance of the project to this DMP. In particular, WP leaders together with WP6 will work towards making instrument data, simulated data, software and workflows as FAIR as possible using the above-mentioned restrictions and boundary conditions, and the emerging infrastructure at DESY. Otherwise, as mentioned, the FAIR and data policies of the host labs of EAJADE R&D activities apply.

5. DATA SECURITY

Data security for all documents and data sets uploaded to Zenodo relies on Zenodo's security measures. Data security for confidential deliverables relies on DESY's Sync&Share infrastructure, adhering to Nextcloud standards.

The reference data sets benefit from a guaranteed availability for 10 years at the hosting facilities.

Ontologies and code rely on GitHub.com infrastructure.

6. ETHICAL ASPECTS

The handling of the protection of personal data (POPD) requirements in EAJADE receives particular attention.

In the framework of EAJADE, various surveys will be made. Personal data collected for them will be deleted after anonymisation or aggregation. Other personal data, like a project's "who's who" document or the list of attendees to training, workshops and conference events, will be stored in the collaboration space with restricted access to the project's contributors.

Consent will be obtained before any public dissemination of presentations and photos.

7. ACKNOWLEDGEMENTS

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8. REFERENCES